

Veli Pasha Mosque in Rethymno

also known as “Mastaba Mosque, Veli Pasha Tekke”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Abrahamic, Islam, Mosque, Sufism, Religious Place, Language, Turkic, Islamic Traditions, Sunni, Hanafi, Sufi, Bektashi

The Veli Pasha Mosque at Mastabas was built shortly after the Ottoman conquest of Rethymno in 1646. In 1651, the mosque appears in the records of the qadi (judge) of Rethymno. The mosque complex includes the nine-domed mosque, measuring 16.6 by 16.2 meters, as well as eight vaulted cells, and a nearby tekke (communal dervish compound) used by the Bektashi Sufi order. Following the population transfer between Greece and Turkey of 1924 which expelled the island's Muslim population, the mosque was no longer used for prayer, and was damaged during the bombings of 1941. Between 2000-2006, the mosque was restored and is now the Rethymno Palaeontological Museum. While the mosque is within the boundaries of modern-day Rethymno, in the mid-seventeenth century at the time of its founding, the site was located outside of the city proper.

Date Range: 1646 CE - 1924 CE

Region: Veli Pasha Mosque Complex in Rethymno, Crete

Region tags: Crete, Greece, Rethymno

This map shows the mosque, the row of connecting vaulted cells, and the tekke of the the Bektashi tariqa.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi. 8. Kitap, 1. Cilt. Trans. Seyit Ali Kahraman. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.
- Source 2: Evliya Çelebi Seyahatnamesi. VIII. Kitap. Transcribed by Seyit Ali Kahraman, Yücel Dağlı, Robert Dankoff. Yapı Kredi Yayınları, İstanbul, 2003.
- Source 3: Dimitris Loupis, ΕΒΛΙΑ ΤΣΕΛΕΜΠΙ ΟΔΟΙΠΟΡΙΚΟ ΣΤΗΝ ΕΛΛΑΔΑ. Athens, 2005.

Notes: Evliya Çelebi describes the mosque shortly after its founding in his travelogue concerning Crete. A transcription of the Ottoman Turkish original into the Latin alphabet has been published (Source 2), as has a translation into Modern Turkish (Source 1) and a translation into Modern Greek (Source 3).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.rethymno.guide/events-calendar/location/11-paleontological-museum>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The mosque complex is on a slight rise, but not at the top of any of the surrounding hills.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: At the time of its construction, the mosque complex was not located within an urbanized area; today (2023), the city of Rethymno has expanded to encompass it.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: At the time of its founding, between 1646 and 1651 CE, the mosque was located outside the city limits of Rethymno. The site had been the campsite of the Ottoman army that besieged Rethymno in 1646. As shown in a watercolor by Edward Lear painted 7 May 1864, in the late 19th century the mosque complex remained outside the city limits, on a slight hill surrounded by agricultural fields.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The mosque is a 10-minute walk (600) meters) from the city walls of the Old Town of Rethymno.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Today (in 2023), the mosque complex includes the Veli Pasha mosque, the Bektashi tekke, 8 adjoining vaulted dervish cells, the sheikh quarters. From 1671 or earlier to ca. 1924, an Islamic cemetery was also present.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Individual

– Social

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: More research is needed into the building phases of the complex.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: The south side of the mosque collapsed due to bombing in 1941.
The complex had also suffered damage after abandonment in 1924.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Natural phenomena

Notes: Disuse from 1924 onwards contributed to decline of structures.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: From 2000-2006, the mosque was restored. Previously, in 1941, the south face of the mosque had been destroyed by wartime bombing.

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: Not known, although it is likely that modifications were made over time.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The mosque was used to worship God, understood as the monotheistic, all-powerful deity of Islamic faith.

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: The site is affiliated with the Bektashi tariqa of Sufi dervishes.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Notes: The site had been the campsite of the Ottoman army that besieged Rethymno in 1646.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: There is a slight geographical rise at the site of Mastabas where the mosque was built.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The eight vaulted cells and the two-story sheikh quarters are attached to each other in a row. The minaret is attached to the mosque.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque of Veli Pasha is the central feature of the site.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: While the majority of the stone is sourced locally, marble spolia present in the vaulted dervish cells may not be from the local environment.

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The stone used to construct the mosque and surrounding structures is similar to that of other mosques and houses of the Old Town of Rethymno.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The interior of the mosque features square pillars and pointed arches that support the domes, in a style that resembles the Grand Mosque of Bursa (completed 1400 CE) on a much smaller scale.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

Notes: The south side of the mosque has been reconstructed; as a result, the original mihrab is no longer present. It is possible that the mihrab featured geometric decoration.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: There are inscriptions on the base of the minaret (1204 AH) and the tekke (a plaque from 1310 AH referencing 1055 AH).

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: The vegetal decoration above the mosque entryway, consisting of vines, is carved in relief.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Reliefs above the entrance to the mosque consist of vegetal motifs, primarily vines.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Notes: Interior of mosque has been restored with plaster and cut stone; original interior decorations, if they existed, are not present.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions can be found on the base of the minaret (1204 AH) and attached to the tekke (a plaque from 1310 AH commemorating a founding of 1055 AH).

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None.

Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Windows

Notes: Two levels of windows on three sides of the mosque mean that the interior receives ample daylight.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: A cemetery was part of the mosque complex, and was mentioned in Evliya Celebi's account of his travels to Crete between 1668 and 1671.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: While a cemetery was once part of the mosque complex, tombstones have been removed from their original locations and are in storage within the complex.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: A supreme high god is worshipped, but is generally not considered to be physically present or manifested at the religious site.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sir Arthur Evans reported divination practices from Bektashis in Albania ca. 1901; it is possible that Bektashis in Crete practiced divination as well, but would require further research.

Reference: Evans, Arthur. "Mycenaean Tree and Pillar Cult and Its Mediterranean Relations", 1901.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and djinn may be considered to be present.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors prayed to one supreme deity.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Some visitors may have communicated with angels and/or djinn at this site.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 50-300

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Prayers occurred several times per day: in addition to the five mandatory daily prayers, the Bektashis at this tekke may have had additional prayers in the morning and midday.

Reference: Jazexhi, Olsi. "The Bektashi Tarikah of Dervishes", 2007.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: While Friday prayer in community (at a mosque) was generally considered mandatory for Muslim men during the time of the mosque's operation, it was optional for

Muslim women, who could pray either in community or alone.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque complex included a soup kitchen that served food twice daily to rich and poor; it is likely that meals were more festive on Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Meals were connected to the Imaret (soup kitchen).

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is likely that Eid ul-Adha and Eid ul-Fitr were celebrated here.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Dervishes travelled between lodges.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: While the most well-known Bektashi leaders on Crete were men, the subject of women's Sufi practices on Crete requires further research. Within the Bektashi order, women participated in the rites alongside men (Tschudi p. 1162). See reference on Bektashi women's practices in Anatolia for a comparative study.

Reference: Ghodrati Vayghan, Manizhe. "Sufi Ladies in Bektashi Order in Anatolia During Seljuks of Rum", 2015.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: Dervishes travelled between lodges.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: Previously, fountains were a part of the complex.

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: Prior to the expansion of the city, the mosque was located on the road approaching Rethymno from the south.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: No specific religious texts are associated with this mosque, but religious texts would have been read here.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Veli Pasha Mosque in Rethymno, Zilli, Mehmed (Evliya). *Evliya çelebi seyahatnamesi*. Translated by Seyit Kahraman. Vol. 8/1. İstanbul: Yapı Kredi Yayınları, 2010.

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Entry/Answer References

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